

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INTEGRATION OF NATIONAL MUSIC INTO THE CURRICULA OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17421487>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th October 2025

Accepted: 20th October 2025

Online: 21st October 2025

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

In the process of today's globalization, the preservation of national values in the education system and their introduction into the consciousness of young people is considered one of the priorities of state policy. Higher educational institutions act not only as educational institutions, but also as social institutions that form high spirituality, national pride, and aesthetic taste in students. From this point of view, the issue of integrating national music into the curricula of the higher education system is of particular relevance.

In the process of today's globalization, the preservation of national values in the education system and their introduction into the consciousness of young people is considered one of the priorities of state policy. Higher educational institutions act not only as educational institutions, but also as social institutions that form high spirituality, national pride, and aesthetic taste in students. From this point of view, the issue of integrating national music into the curricula of the higher education system is of particular relevance. Because musical art is the most powerful tool that directly affects the human soul, enriches the spiritual world of young people, and celebrates national values. The integration of national music into educational programs serves, first of all, to expand the aesthetic worldview of students, develop their artistic thinking, and strengthen national identity. Uzbek folk music - Shashmaqom, folklore melodies and songs, traditional instruments, classical songs - for centuries played an important role in educating national consciousness, expressing the dreams and aspirations, historical memory and cultural heritage of the people. The introduction of this heritage into the higher education system will allow not only to teach musicological knowledge, but also to strengthen the national spirit in students of each direction. After all, the student period is the most responsible stage in the formation of a person's worldview, value system, aesthetic taste, and creative potential. The effectiveness of the integration of national music into the process of higher education is manifested, first of all, in the unity of education and upbringing. The use of national melodies and songs in educational programs forms not only the student's musical knowledge, but also their moral and aesthetic views. For example, in the process of studying maqom or folklore songs, students not only perceive the melody and rhythm, but also deeply feel the ideas of patriotism, humanism, goodness, and love embodied in their content. From this point of view, national music plays an invaluable role in the student's striving for perfection, understanding national identity, and upbringing in the spirit of respect for values. In addition, national music

develops creative thinking in students, since the process of playing melodies, singing songs, or analyzing their content requires independent thinking, emotional expression, and creative exploration from the student.

Another important effect of integrating national music into the educational process is to familiarize students with the rich heritage of our national culture and teach them to find their place in global culture. Currently, as a result of the widespread dissemination of foreign music, certain changes are observed in the tastes of young people. If insufficient attention is paid to national music in the higher education system, the musical taste of young people may be formed one-sidedly, and they may distance themselves from national heritage. Therefore, it is important to regularly introduce national musical works into the educational process, to involve students in listening to melodies and songs, performing them, and analyzing them. Through this process, students develop not only musical literacy, but also devotion to national values, self-awareness, and a sense of patriotism. The formation of aesthetic culture in students through music is also one of the results of integration. Because music cultivates aesthetic feelings, develops the ability to perceive beauty. Through the use of national music in the higher education system, students gain a deeper understanding of the beauty of nature and life, become more sensitive to works of art, and develop their artistic taste. Especially in the process of playing national instruments or singing folk songs, students receive creative pleasure, have the opportunity to express their aesthetic feelings through musical activity. Through this, they rise not only in musical, but also in spiritual terms. The effectiveness of the integration process is that the inclusion of national music in the curriculum encourages students to acquire comprehensive knowledge. Because in this process, they assimilate not only musical theory and practice, but also information inextricably linked with history, philosophy, ethnography, literature, and art. For example, in the process of studying maqoms, students also become acquainted with Eastern philosophy, Uzbek literature, and folk oral art. This, in turn, expands the general worldview of students and ensures interdisciplinary integration. The social impact of integrating national music into educational programs is also significant. With the help of such an approach, higher educational institutions strengthen students' respect for national values, a culture of intercultural communication, the desire for creative research, and social activity. Students become more active in society by actively participating in various events - musical evenings, concerts, festivals. Also, the educational process based on national music prepares them to promote their culture abroad and bring our national heritage to the world stage. In conclusion, the integration of national music into the curricula of higher educational institutions is not only a means of providing musical knowledge, but also an effective means of developing spiritual and moral qualities, aesthetic taste, national pride, and creative thinking in students. The main results of this process are manifested in the student's striving for perfection as a person, a deep understanding of national identity, and an increased need to value and preserve national heritage within global culture. Therefore, one of the most pressing tasks today is the expansion of lessons in higher educational institutions based on national music, its introduction into the educational process with the help of new pedagogical technologies, and the enhancement of the artistic and aesthetic worldview of students..

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